

CONCEPT IN LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL STUDIES

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Abstract. this article is about concept in linguistic and cultural studies that deals with the linguistic picture of the world in the linguoculturological aspect. In addition, author gives several possible notions based on the topic from prominent linguists who contributed in the sphere of linguoculturology.

Keywords: *reality, society, culture, ethnolinguistics, linguoculturology, stereotypes.*
For more than a century, the question of the relationship between language and culture has been worrying the minds of many famous scientists, but to this day this question remains open. The approach to language as an entity that is in close connection with the surrounding reality, society, culture, and the understanding of it as a social phenomenon are present in philosophy and philology almost from the moment of their emergence. There are many opinions on the problem of the relationship between language and culture. As an example, we can cite the words of the largest scientist, the founder of the American school of ethnolinguistics E. Sepira: "Culture can be defined as what a given society does and thinks. Language is how people think" [1]. E. Sepir and B. Whorf developed the "hypothesis of linguistic relativity".

According to the theory, all researchers who are seriously engaged in the problem of the relationship between language and culture, language and thinking, apply, since it is with the help of this hypothesis that those facts of language that are difficult to explain in any other way can be comprehended. This hypothesis is based on the statement that people see the world differently - through the prism of their native language. For its supporters, the reality around us exists insofar as it is reflected in language. But if each language reflects reality in a special way, characteristic only for it, then, consequently, languages differ in their "linguistic pictures of the world". E. Sepir wrote about the interdependence of language and culture: "Language does not exist outside of culture, i.e. outside of the socially inherited set of practical skills and ideas that characterize our way of life" [1]. He further explains that "the language in its vocabulary more or less accurately reflects the culture it serves, and it is absolutely true that the history of language and the history of culture develop in parallel" [1]. The Sepir - Whorf hypothesis highlights scientific provisions: 1) language determines the way of

thinking of the people who speak it; 2) the way of knowing the real world depends on what languages the cognizing subjects think in. "We dissect nature in the direction suggested by our language. We distinguish certain categories and types in the world of phenomena not at all because they are self-evident; on the contrary, the world appears to us as a kaleidoscopic stream of impressions that must be organized by our consciousness, which means mainly by a language system stored in our consciousness. We dissect the world, organize it into concepts and distribute meanings this way and not otherwise, mainly because we are parties to an agreement prescribing such systematization. This is valid for a certain language collective and is fixed in the system of models of our language". The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis aroused interest and withstood criticism. Nevertheless, with the help of this hypothesis, new directions in linguistics were formed – ethnolinguistics and linguoculturology.

At one time, V. von. Humboldt tried to solve the problem of the relationship between language and culture, expressing thoughts that material and spiritual culture are embodied in language; every culture is national, its national character is expressed in language through a special vision of the world; language has an internal form specific to each people, which is an expression of the "national spirit", his culture; language is an intermediary link between a person and the world around him. He wrote: "Language is the united spiritual energy of the people, miraculously imprinted in certain sounds, in this guise and through the interconnection of its sounds, understandable to all speakers and exciting approximately the same energy in them" [2]. Thus, language is the main form of expression and reflection of culture. Humboldt believed that "languages are hieroglyphs in which a person encloses the world and his imagination; despite the fact that the world and imagination, constantly creating picture after picture according to the laws of similarity, remain generally unchanged, languages develop by themselves, become more complicated, expand. Through the diversity of languages, the richness of the world and the diversity of what we know in it are revealed to us; and human existence becomes broader for us, since languages in distinct and effective features give us different ways of thinking and perception. The language always embodies the uniqueness of an entire nation, so it should not be afraid of either sophistication or excess of imagination, which some people consider undesirable. What they give us at once is full, pure and simple human nature, but if we penetrate into the depths of their secrets, a fresh stream of unfading fantasy of other people's bursts into our dry rationality, enclosing every impression that the young world gives to their

not yet dulled feelings, in the shell of a living and immobile image” [2]. In our opinion, the image of the world is hidden in the consciousness of a particular people, which is actualized with the help of linguistic means. And the study of the means of verbalization of the surrounding reality, which is in the consciousness of the ethnic group, helps to get closer to the national culture.

D.S. Likhachev, considering the essence of the concept, emphasizes that “the national language is not only a means of communication, a sign system for transmitting messages. The national language in potency is like a “substitute” of culture, an indicator of culture” [3]. He further explains his idea that “if we study the entire sphere of concepts (or, in other words, the “conceptual sphere” of the national language), then there turns out to be an extraordinary wealth and the closest connection with the culture of the people – with literature and oral folk art in the first place” [3].

We find similar statements in E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov: “At any moment in the development of culture, the language serving it reflects it fully and adequately, in other words, society determines the progress in language, especially its mobile levels; on the other hand, it is permissible to talk about a certain impact of language on the development of culture (in other words, society determines the progress in language, especially its mobile levels; on the other hand, it is permissible to talk about a certain impact of language on the development of culture (in particular, in the field of folklore and fiction) [4]. According to the following researcher of intercultural communication S.G. Ter-Minasova, “language is a mirror of the surrounding world, it reflects reality and creates its own picture of the world, specific and unique for each language and, accordingly, people, ethnic group, speech collective using this language as a means of communication” [5].

In our opinion, language plays an important role in the internationalization of culture. The contact and mutual influence of different cultures is reflected in the language in the form of lexical borrowings. Culture does not exist outside of human activity. Language is a social phenomenon, and it is inextricably linked with native speakers. And culture, as a creation of the people, correlates with the language of representatives of a certain nation. The formation of cultural stereotypes is impossible without the participation of language, which serves as an instrument for the formation of the “spirit of the people”. N.I. Tolstoy believes that “the correlative links of language and culture are diverse, stable and strong. Language can be considered as an instrument of culture, even as one of its hypostases (especially literary language, sacred language or folklore language)

and, as such, can be described through signs common to all cultural phenomena. On the other hand, language and culture can be compared as independent, autonomous semiotic systems, in many respects isomorphic and mutually mapped” [6].

Language and culture are interconnected, and changes in them occur in parallel. Language reflects reality, and culture is an integral component of this reality that a person perceives.

Language is a specific part of culture. It is most closely connected with thinking, which cannot be divorced from speech activity: thinking, a person speaks mentally. Language and consciousness are two necessary conditions for the existence of a society to create its own spiritual culture.

Further consideration of the relationship between language and culture leads to the idea that language is a fact of culture, firstly, because it is its constituent component that we inherit from our ancestors; secondly, language is the main means of assimilation of culture; thirdly, it is the most important of all cultural phenomena, since if we want to understand the essence of culture – science, religion, literature, then we must consider these phenomena as codes formed like a language, since natural language has the best developed model. We can confirm this idea with the words of S. G. Ter-Minasova: “Language is a mirror of culture, it reflects not only the real world surrounding a person, not only the real conditions of his life, but also the public consciousness of the people, their mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions, customs, morality, value system, attitude, vision of the world” [5]. Therefore, language can be considered the guardian of culture, spiritual values of the people, their worldview. Having enclosed ideas about the world in its structure, the language reproduces them in the speech of its native speakers.

Thus, the language not only reflects modern culture, but also captures its previous states and transmits its values from generation to generation. Or, in other words, language in relation to culture has the cumulative property of accumulating axiological, spiritual and lexico-semantic features of culture and inheriting them. The problem of the relationship between language and culture is interdisciplinary and its solution is possible with the help of several sciences.

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